

FRIDGE: Federated Research Infrastructure by Data Governance Extension

Validation of satellite TREs for AI workflows

1. Summary

FRIDGE enables Trusted Research Environments (TREs) to extend their capabilities to include access to the AI Research Resource (AIRR), the UK's national AI supercomputer facilities. FRIDGE provides both technical and governance solutions to allow work on sensitive data to be conducted using the capabilities of AIRR from within a TRE.

Under the shared-responsibility model, the TRE Provider and the Hosting Organisation are responsible for the FRIDGE itself and the tenancy that surrounds it respectively.

This document focuses on the FRIDGE itself and the workflow processing model it adopts. For further details of how the FRIDGE tenancy is designed, please see our [architecture documentation](#).

2. How a FRIDGE works

A FRIDGE instance comprises two Kubernetes clusters: an **access** cluster and an **isolated** cluster.

The access cluster is the entry point to the FRIDGE. It contains services that allow forwarding of traffic between the remote TRE and the isolated cluster, where the primary FRIDGE services are housed.

The isolated cluster itself contains a workflow orchestration tool ([Argo Workflows](#)), S3-compatible object storage ([MinIO](#)), and the FRIDGE API.

The FRIDGE API is a REST API interface that exposes a subset of the capabilities of Argo Workflows and MinIO to TRE Users. It is exposed to TRE Users through a proxy service in the access cluster.

Argo Workflows is a Kubernetes-based, cloud-native workflow orchestration tool, and is the core workflow tooling included in FRIDGE.

MinIO provides S3-compatible object storage, allowing easy upload and download of data to and from the FRIDGE instance.

2.1. FRIDGE API

Figure 1 shows the OpenAPI Swagger documentation for the FRIDGE API. It allows interaction with both Argo Workflows and MinIO. We anticipate the TRE Users interacting with the API through a web interface within their home TRE, rather than directly making API calls.

FRIDGE API 0.3.0 OAS 3.1

[/openapi.json](#)

FRIDGE API allows you to interact with the FRIDGE cluster.

Argo Workflows

You can manage workflows in Argo Workflows using this API.

It provides endpoints to list workflows, get details of a specific workflow, list workflow templates, get details of a specific workflow template, and submit workflows based on templates.

Authorize

Argo Workflows

GET	/workflows/{namespace}	Get Workflows	
GET	/workflows/{namespace}/{workflow_name}/log	Get Workflow Log	
GET	/workflows/{namespace}/{workflow_name}	Get Single Workflow	
GET	/workflowtemplates/{namespace}	List Workflow Templates	
GET	/workflowtemplates/{namespace}/{template_name}	Get Workflow Template	
POST	/workflovevents/from_template/	Submit Workflow From Template	
s3			
POST	/object/{bucket}/upload	Upload Object	
GET	/object/{bucket}/{file_name}	Get Object	
DELETE	/object/{bucket}/{file_name}	Delete Object	
POST	/object/move	Move Object	
POST	/object/bucket	Create Bucket	

Figure 1. OpenAPI Swagger documentation for the FRIDGE API

Using the FRIDGE API as the method through which users interact with the FRIDGE services allows us to maintain a high degree of control over the capabilities they are allowed to access. It can also be easily expanded in the future, and allows us to present a consistent interface to users even if we change the specific software tools implementing backend functionality.

Furthermore, using Kubernetes RBAC, the capabilities of the FRIDGE API service are restricted such that the only services it can communicate with are Argo Workflows and MinIO. If a user were to compromise it, or gain access to its service token, they would have no greater privileges than those already exposed by the API itself.

3. Workflow processing model

FRIDGE uses a workflow processing model. TRE Users use the FRIDGE API to upload data and analysis scripts, run analysis workflows, and retrieve the results of those workflows.

The typical interaction of the user with the FRIDGE is envisaged as follows:

1. Upload of data and scripts from existing TRE to object storage within FRIDGE
2. Transfer of data and scripts to block storage within FRIDGE

3. Initiation of workflow to perform analysis and processing of the uploaded data using the uploaded script
4. Results of the workflow are placed in object storage within FRIDGE
5. Results are downloaded from object storage within FRIDGE to the home TRE of the user

The software that runs the workflows themselves is Argo Workflows.

A *Workflow* in Argo is, conceptually, a set of steps where each step is completed using a container. A Workflow can be a single step, or many steps that build on each other, with the input for each step being the output of the preceding step. A single Workflow is intended as an ephemeral, single run of a particular set of steps, and is defined using a YAML template.

A *Workflow Template* is a reusable definition of a Workflow. It can be parameterised such that the exact Workflow created from the Template can be variable. For example, a Template can be created such that the exact container image to be used for a given step must be supplied at runtime as an input parameter. The definition exists in the Kubernetes cluster, and in the current FRIDGE model, is created by the TRE Administrators.

Using Kubernetes RBAC, Argo Workflows is restricted to running workflows in a single Kubernetes namespace. That namespace is secured with several technical restrictions to reduce the risk of users gaining access to the host or moving laterally within the isolated cluster:

- *Restricted* level Pod Security Standards require all containers to run as non-root, with no direct host access possible
- Cilium Network Policies prevent network ingress to, or egress from, the workflow namespace, with the only exception being traffic to and from MinIO

In principle, the workflow could create any kind of Kubernetes resource (e.g. pods, jobs, services). In practice, the Workflow Controller, which instantiates the workflows, is restricted to creating Pods using RBAC. Thus, users interacting with Argo Workflows through the FRIDGE API cannot create resources outside the intended namespace.

Figure 2. The Argo Workflows web interface. Shown are a set of successfully completed workflow runs on the Dawn supercomputer.

Argo Workflows offers a powerful web interface (Fig. 2) that, among many other features, allows creation and monitoring of workflows. Although TRE administrators can access the web interface using the Kubernetes API, it is not exposed to TRE Users. TRE Users must use the FRIDGE API, which in turn sends their requests to Argo Workflows server API endpoints.

For example, to submit a workflow based on a template, a request is sent to the “workflowevents/from_template” API endpoint. Figure 3 shows a `curl` request being sent to trigger a workflow. Figure 4 shows the response from the server confirming its receipt and the name of the workflow being created.

```
curl -X 'POST' \  
  'http://localhost:8442/workflowevents/from_template?verbose=false' \  
  -H 'accept: application/json' \  
  -H 'Content-Type: application/json' \  
  -d '{  
    "namespace": "argo-workflows",  
    "template_name": "intel-batched-matmul",  
    "parameters": {}  
  }'
```

Figure 3. An API request sent to the FRIDGE API using `curl`. It is requesting that a workflow based on the workflow template “intel-batched-matmul” be created in the namespace “argo-workflows”.

```
{  
  "workflow_submitted": {  
    "namespace": "argo-workflows",  
    "template_name": "intel-batched-matmul",  
    "parameters": {}  
  },  
  "status": 200,  
  "response": {  
    "name": "intel-batched-matmul-bwsw",  
    "namespace": "argo-workflows",  
    "status": null,  
    "created_at": "2026-04-17T12:57:11Z"  
  }  
}
```

Figure 4. The response to the preceding API request.

4. Testing GPU and non-GPU workflows

We developed FRIDGE for three target platforms: Microsoft Azure, Dawn, and Isambard AI. Each platform required its own deployment model encompassing the creation of an appropriate tenancy and the deployment of the FRIDGE inside that tenancy.

We aimed to validate that the workflow processing model could successfully be used via a secure tunnel from a remote site to run user workflows on our target platforms.

4.1. Target platform compute

4.1.1. Azure Kubernetes Service

We used the Microsoft Azure platform to prototype the FRIDGE and FRIDGE tenancy. The Azure Kubernetes Service (AKS) test platform was intended for non-GPU workload testing. For our isolated cluster, we created a cluster with two node pools: a system pool, using Standard_B2als_v2 VMs (2 vCPUs, 4 GB memory), and a user pool, using Standard_B4als_v2 VMs (4 vCPUs, 8 GB memory).

On AKS, we tested the principles of moving data into the FRIDGE, moving data within the FRIDGE, running a workload, and retrieving the output, using a secure tunnel from a remote site representing an external TRE.

4.1.2. DAWN

Dawn is an OpenStack private cloud. A FRIDGE tenancy can be declared in a similar way to on Azure. Development for Dawn progressed to the stage where we could run test GPU workflows.

Dawn's GPU offering consists of 1024 Intel Ponte Vecchio Data Centre GPU Max units (PVCs). A single GPU-enabled compute node comprises four PVCs. Each PVC is exposed in the software stack as two independent XPU devices, each with its own high-bandwidth memory stack. Thus, a single PVC node offers eight effectively independent logical XPU devices.

During testing, our Dawn FRIDGE was configured with K3s clusters (Kubernetes v1.34). Our isolated cluster comprised three nodes: a control plane node and two quarter PVC nodes. Each quarter PVC node thus offered us two independent logical XPU devices for testing.

4.1.3. Isambard AI

Isambard AI required a more complex initial set up process for the tenancy, with several technical challenges specific to Isambard AI that needed to be overcome. Thus, a full FRIDGE deployment was not used during testing. Instead, the primary test was a deployment of the isolated cluster only.

Isambard AI's GPU offering is based on NVIDIA, rather than Intel. The Isambard AI supercomputer comprises 5448 NVIDIA GH200 Grace Hopper Superchips. Each of these has a H100 GPU with 96 Gb RAM. Each compute node on Isambard AI hosts four superchips. Our initial target was a single compute node for the isolated cluster on Isambard AI.

Although GPU workflows have successfully been tested on Isambard AI independently of FRIDGE, given the difference in architecture between the two sites, we focused on demonstrating that the workflow process worked on Isambard AI. Adaptation of our test GPU workflows to NVIDIA-based chips will be performed in future iterations of the project.

4.2. Test workflows

4.2.1. Non-GPU workflows

On AKS and Isambard AI, we ran a simple non-GPU task as a test of the workflow-based model.

The FRIDGE API was exposed to a development machine via an SSH tunnel, with the development machine acting as a user endpoint.

For this test, we, acting as a TRE Administrator, set up a Workflow Template with input parameters to allow users to specify 1) which container image to use, 2) the filename of an archive containing the test data, and 3) the filename of the script to run on the container image.

The steps in this workflow were to

1. Upload test data from remote location
2. Upload Python script from remote location
3. Retrieve workflow template
4. Submit workflow template with appropriate parameters
5. Retrieve workflow outputs from object storage, downloading to the remote location

Each of these steps was performed via the FRIDGE API.

We set up the workflow template to automatically retrieve the data and script from object storage, storing them on a temporary scratch disk for the duration of the workflow.

The screenshot shows an HTML report for an MNE Raw example. The 'Info' section is expanded, showing the following details:

General	
Filename(s)	sample_audvis_raw.fif
MNE object type	Raw
Measurement date	2002-12-03 at 19:01:10 UTC
Participant	Unknown
Experimenter	MEG
Acquisition	
Duration	00:04:01 (HH:MM:SS)
Sampling frequency	600.61 Hz
Time points	144,149
Channels	
Magnetometers	302
Gradiometers	203 and 3 bad
EEG	50 and 3 bad
EDG	1
Stimulus	0
Head & sensor digitization	146 points
Filters	
Highpass	0.10 Hz
Lowpass	172.18 Hz
Projections	PCA-v1 (off) PCA-v2 (off) PCA-v3 (off)

Figure 5. Output from the non-GPU test workflow, downloaded to the remote location.

Our example workflow used some data included with the neuroimaging Python package [MNE-Python](#), performing some basic preprocessing, and producing a HTML report. Figure 5 shows some of the resulting output.

4.2.2. GPU workflows

On Dawn, we performed a set of test GPU workflows.

We used a combination of simple, single-step workflows designed to show that GPU processing was possible in our workflow framework, and multi-step workflows designed to demonstrate how a typical user workflow might work.

4.2.2.1. Synthetic compute test

We wanted a simple, self-contained test verifying that the GPUs were available to the Kubernetes cluster and that they were functioning correctly.

GPUs are designed around massively parallel floating-point processing units. Matrix multiplications are a good test of the capabilities of a GPU, since they rely so heavily on exactly that type of processing. Thus, we chose a batched matrix multiplication test.

For our initial test, we wrote a Python test script that:

1. Verified the presence of Intel GPUs using PyTorch
2. Simulated two sets of 64 2048 × 2048 matrices
3. Used PyTorch's bmm (batched matrix multiplication) function to multiply the two sets of matrices together
4. Calculated the mean time to perform the multiplications over 200 iterations

Once the workflow was completed, we used the FRIDGE API to retrieve the workflow logs, which showed the output of the script.

A single Intel PVC stack took ~24.78 seconds to complete this task, or, on average, ~0.12 seconds per matrix batch.

The test could easily be parameterised to allow modification of matrix size, batch size, or iteration count to benchmark the capabilities of the GPU over a range of scenarios that would reflect characteristics such as peak throughput, memory bandwidth, and sustained performance.

4.2.2.2. *Small model training test*

To examine a more realistic scenario, we introduced a multi-step example that required more than triggering a self-contained Workflow Template. We fit a small convolutional neural network (CNN) to the CIFAR10 dataset. This is more directly representative of the kinds of tasks used for machine learning and AI training workflows.

CIFAR10 is a collection of 60000 32×32 colour images showing ten different classes of object. It is a foundational dataset in machine learning and computer vision. We used a small CNN to classify the category to which each image belonged.

We first transferred the archived CIFAR10 dataset to object storage within the FRIDGE via the FRIDGE API. It was then transferred to block storage within the FRIDGE. Within the workflow, the CIFAR10 archive is unzipped within the local storage and then loaded by PyTorch. PyTorch was then used to fit a small CNN using a single stack of the Intel PVC attached to the node.

Our test workflow was able to process ~25893 images per second on a single stack of an Intel PVC GPU, successfully demonstrating the use of a GPU for a real AI/machine learning task using our workflow model, triggered from a remote location through the FRIDGE API.

4.2.2.3. *Distributed training test*

One important additional use case is using multiple GPUs when running AI training workflows. Thus, an important additional test was to demonstrate that we could successfully trigger single-node, multiple-GPU workflows.

As noted earlier, a single Intel PVC comprises two independent stacks. Effectively, this is the same as a multiple-GPU scenario. To PyTorch, each stack appears as an independent GPU. We adapted our small model training workflow to distribute training across the available stacks within our single GPU test node.

This approach would straightforwardly extend to any number of GPU stacks available within a single node.

This run showed significant speed-ups over the single GPU stack benchmark workflow, hitting a processing speed of ~37656 images per second. Thus, we successfully demonstrated performance increases with distributed training.

5. Summary

We performed a set of test workflows across our three target platforms: AKS, Isambard AI, and Dawn. We first demonstrated that our implementation of workflow processing functioned across all three platforms. We successfully ran simple non-GPU workflows across all three test platforms. We then ran three GPU-workflow tests. We demonstrated:

1. Basic GPU functionality was in-place and accessible
2. Machine-learning/AI training workflows using GPUs were possible
3. Distributing training across multiple GPUs on a single node is possible

All interactions with the FRIDGE took place over a secure tunnel from a remote device. We have thus demonstrated that performing AI workflows using GPUs is viable under the FRIDGE model.

Our next steps are to develop FRIDGE further for production use cases with real sensitive datasets. The AIRR-BRIDGE project will follow-on from FRIDGE. AIRR-BRIDGE will work closely with the AIRR sites. We will be working closely with real users and data owners to ensure that FRIDGE meets their requirements and enables cutting-edge research with the cutting-edge compute capabilities of the AIRR supercomputers.

Some additional steps will include testing multiple-node functionality. Multiple-node training workflows were out of scope for initial testing on FRIDGE. We have demonstrated multiple-GPU training successfully, and multiple-node training would be a natural extension. In addition, our demonstrations here have focussed on training workflows. Further development of the FRIDGE model would be required to allow for inference workflows. We will also look to align our work closely with [TREvolution](#) projects. For example, [Five Safes TES](#) has a similar focus on execution of standardised workflows.

In summary, we have developed a satellite TRE model in which AI workflows can be successfully run on AIRR supercomputers from a remote location. We developed both a model for a secure tenancy on the AIRR supercomputers, and appropriate services that can run within that tenancy to allow workflows to run using sensitive data securely. In this report, we have shown how our workflow model functions in practice, demonstrating how it can be used to upload relevant data and scripts from a remote location using a secure connection, trigger AI workflows on supercomputers, and return outputs to a secure remote location.